

AUDIO-TACTILE FEEDBACK IN MUSICAL GESTURE PRIMITIVES: FINGER PRESSING

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ABSTRACT

We present a study on the effect of auditory and vibrotactile cues in a finger-pressing task. During a training phase subjects learned three target forces, and had to reproduce them during an experiment, under different feedback conditions. Results show that audio-tactile augmentation allowed subjects to achieve memorized target forces with improved accuracy. A tabletop device capable of recording normal force and displaying vibrotactile feedback was implemented to run several experiments. This study is first in a series of planned investigations on the role of audio-haptic feedback and perception in relation to musical gestures primitives.

1. INTRODUCTION

The synergy of tactile, auditory and kinesthetic cues generally plays a central role while performing on acoustic and electro-acoustic musical instruments. Indeed, several studies [1–3] support the idea that tactile and kinesthetic feedback inform sophisticated control strategies which enable experienced musicians to achieve top performance levels (e.g. precise timing, accurate intonation), and support expressivity and self-monitoring.

Conversely, while modern digital musical interfaces (DMIs) can track to different extent input gestures, they provide haptic feedback only as by-product of their built-in mechanics, if any. This missing physical link between DMIs and performers prevents the latter to enter the engagement and embodiment normally established in actual interactions with traditional instruments, and alters the action-perception loop [4]. In this perspective, the addition of advanced audio-haptic to future DMIs is expected to offer enhanced playability, performance and expressivity. Currently, however, the development of actuated musical interfaces is often grounded on practice and intuition, leading to the production of one-of-a-kind devices [5], while only rarely a systematic approach is taken into account [6], or general guidelines are produced [7–9].

To overcome this, we suggest that a scientifically founded, multidisciplinary approach is necessary, which

should involve experts from fields such as human-machine interaction, musical practice, applied psychology and engineering. The present work belongs to a series of ongoing investigations aimed at collecting novel qualitative and quantitative results on the role of audio-haptic feedback and perception in interactions with musical instruments and digital musical interfaces. By following a systematic bottom-up approach – starting with focus on gesture primitives observed in instrumental practice (such as pressing, plucking, sliding, etc.) that will be then combined in more articulated ones – we aim at isolating cross-modal and multisensory phenomena, and at identifying gestures and tasks where the auditory and tactile channels appear crucial to musical performance. The long-term goal is to establish well-grounded guidelines for the implementation of actuated musical interfaces.

In this paper a study is presented, which investigates the effect of audio-tactile cues on reaching target finger-pressing forces that have been previously learned in a training phase. Despite considering simplified input gestures and feedback stimuli, our experiment was designed to imitate real-world playing conditions, where musicians would learn the response of an instrument, and would then perform on it by relying on memorized standards (e.g. from kinesthetic memory).

The present work is the continuation of a preliminary study [10] which is here expanded by re-analyzing the experimental data with more fitting and robust statistical methods, and taking into consideration different groups of subjects according to their musical skills. Moreover, an original discussion of the new results has been added, and the general coverage of the experiment extended.

Similar studies on the effect of haptic feedback on finger-force control are e.g. [11, 12], however these do not take into consideration auditory feedback, nor they rely on memorized force targets.

Other studies which make use of actuated interfaces to investigate the effects of auditory and vibrotactile feedback in tasks related to musical performance are e.g. [13–16].

2. EXPERIMENT

The experiment considered the gesture of pressing with the finger on a flat, rigid surface.

Our hypothesis was that auditory and tactile feedback provided interactively by such surface would support subjects in reaching target pressing-force levels.

Figure 1. The touch box interface used in the experiment for recording normal finger forces and providing vibrotactile feedback.

2.1 Apparatus and signal flow

The experiment made use of a tabletop interface developed for this purpose, and housed in a small 3D-printed plastic box (see Figure 1). The touch box interface offers a top panel embedding an Interlink 406 force sensing resistor (FSR) which records normal force. The analog force signal provided by the FSR is fed into an Arduino UNO board which uniformly samples it at 1920 Hz with 10 bit resolution [17]. The Arduino is connected via USB to a host laptop running Pure Data, where the digital data are recorded and used to control a sound synthesis algorithm (see 2.2). The audio signal generated by the synthesis algorithm is output through a RME Fireface 800 audio interface, and used to provide both auditory and vibrotactile feedback: the former is sent to a pair of Sennheiser HD 202 headphones, while the latter is sent to a battery-powered audio amplifier feeding a HiWave HIAX13C02-8/RH audio exciter which is attached to the touch box's top panel.

The box construction was optimized so that the embedded exciter produces vibrations on the touch panel with minimum sound emission. This allows to segregate the auditory and vibrotactile feedback separately.

Additionally, the experimental setup offered an 'OK' button allowing the subjects to mark their currently applied force (see 2.3).

The round-trip latency of a comparable system, which used a similar software/hardware setup for force data acquisition and audio-tactile feedback generation, was measured under 20 ms [17].

2.2 Stimuli and conditions

A simple sine wave was chosen as audio-tactile feedback signal, whose amplitude varied proportionally to the pressing-force applied on the touch panel, thus implementing a metaphor that is commonly found in musical practice, and especially on DMIs. The maximum intensity of the vibrotactile stimulus – corresponding to the maximum force manageable by the FSR – was empirically set to the high-

Figure 2. Characteristic showing input acceleration (g-force) vs. sampled force values (10 bit ADC)

est level that could be produced by the amplifier-exciter combination without perceivable distortion. Similarly, the frequency of the sine wave was empirically chosen in order to maximize the produced vibrotactile sensation [2] at any output level, and consequently set to 200 Hz.

Four *feedback conditions* were considered in the experiment: neutral condition (N), without active feedback; auditory feedback only (A), provided through headphones; auditory and vibrotactile feedback (AV); vibrotactile feedback only (V). In the latter condition, in order to cancel any residual sound emission produced by the interface, a masking noise signal was sent through the headphones.

The experiment was run under three *target conditions* (standards), each corresponding to a different pressing-force level. The targets were chosen empirically according to low, medium and high pressing-forces, within the data range of the interface (values within 0-1023, corresponding to 10-bit resolution): the low target was set to 400, the medium one to 650 and the high target to 850.

By combining the “acceleration-to-voltage” characteristic of the Interlink 406 FSR, and the “voltage-to-ADC values” characteristic of the Arduino UNO board, we extracted the curve shown in Figure 2. This allows one to approximately figure out the acceleration (g-force) values corresponding to the sampled force values output by the Arduino's ADC. Since the curve was obtained from general characteristics provided by the products' data sheet rather than from actual measurements on our interface, it has to be considered as a qualitative reference only.

2.3 Design and procedure

Fourteen subjects (average age 33 years old) participated in the experiment: five of them were pianists, five other musicians and four non-musicians. The musicians were either professionals or in professional training, while the non-musicians had no more than a couple of years of experience with any musical instrument. All subjects reported normal hearing and sense of touch.

The task was to reach a given standard among low, medium or high target forces, under one of the four feedback conditions (N, A, V and AV), thus leading to 12 possi-

ble combinations of target forces and feedback conditions. The test followed a 2-factor within subjects design, where each subject was tested under each combination of conditions. All combinations were repeated 10 times for each subject, resulting in 120 trials that were presented in randomized order.

The subjects sat at a desk, on which the touch box interface and the 'OK' button had been arranged, and were instructed to lean their forearm (dominant hand) on a arm rest and to press one finger on the interface's top panel. Also, they were asked to choose and use the same finger throughout the experiment, and not to touch the box with other fingers.

To begin with, the subjects entered a short *training phase* (lasting 2-4 minutes) in which they had to learn the target pressing-forces, and could freely practice to reproduce them. This was done by providing an additional audio signal through the headphones: three different beeping tones – each corresponding to one target – signaled when the applied force was within an acceptable range (± 50 units) around a target. During this phase, the AV and N feedback conditions were alternated (1-2 minutes each), and when the former condition was on, the subjects were instructed to pay attention to the intensity of the vibrotactile and auditory feedback. During the experimental session, after each block of 30 trials, the subjects were allowed to shortly re-train to refresh their memory.

During the actual trials the beeping tones signaling the targets were removed, and the subjects had to adjust their pressing-force “from memory”, until they believed they had reached the asked target. At that point they had to press the 'OK' button with their free hand, while maintaining the pressing-force on the touch panel.

The experiment was conducted in a sound-proof chamber and each experimental session lasted approximately one hour, including breaks and training.

3. RESULTS

To prevent the possible effect (reported by some of the subjects) of having to press with both hands at the same time, the dependent variable – i.e. pressing-force on the touch panel – was measured as the average over a 10 ms time window, starting 100 ms before the subject pressed the 'OK' button.

The measurements, amounting to 1344 different recordings, included 9 missing data points which were ignored in the analyses.

The data considered for the analysis of each subject was given by the mean over the last 8 repetitions of each combination of conditions, thus regarding the first 2 repetitions as practice. These data are shown in Figure 3, which demonstrates a common trend for both low and medium targets: with audio-tactile feedback (condition AV) the mean results are nearest to the target, while they clearly overshoot with no feedback (condition N); results for the audio-only (A) and vibrotactile-only (V) conditions are somewhere between these extremes.

A large difference in variance over the target force levels was observed both within each subject's 8 repeated

Figure 3. Mean results over all the subjects (errorbars: 95% CI, considering variability due to condition manipulation only, according to [18]). Target forces given by dashed lines: low = 400, medium = 650, high = 850.

Figure 4. Box-plot of results for each target force (median and 25th / 75th percentiles describing between-subjects variability), collapsed over feedback conditions.

measurements and between subjects, shown in Figure 4. This violates the assumption of variance homogeneity for ANOVA. Therefore the data were analyzed using the *aligned rank transform*, a nonparametric method for factorial within-subjects analyses using ANOVA procedures, generalized for n factors in [19].

The analysis shows a significant main effect for the feedback factor ($F_{(3,143)} = 16, p < 0.0001$), when the force data were normalized by subtracting the corresponding target force from each condition (i.e. respectively 400, 650 and 850 for the low, medium and high conditions). No significant effect was observed for the target force level ($F_{(2,143)} = 0.7, p = 0.52$), but the interaction “feedback \times target level” was significant with $F_{(6,143)} = 6.0, p < 0.0001$.

The interaction plots in Figure 5 show that for the low target force, mean errors are much smaller in presence of auditory or audio-tactile feedback (A, AV) than with no

Figure 5. Interaction plots. Top panel: mean errors at the three target forces, presented for each feedback condition. Bottom panel: mean errors at the four feedback conditions, presented for each target force level.

feedback (N). For the high target force, however, the results are almost equivalent at all feedback conditions.

Pairwise comparisons between the feedback conditions, collapsed over the target force levels, were performed by the *Wilcoxon signed-rank test* with *Bonferroni correction*, for significance level cutoff $\alpha = 0.05/5 = 0.01$. These results show significantly different medians between the N-AV pair ($p < 0.0001$), N-A ($p < 0.0001$), N-V ($p < 0.0001$) and V-AV ($p < 0.0001$), but not for A-V ($p = 0.22$) and hardly for A-AV ($p = 0.007$).

Finally, differences between groups of subjects according to their musical skills were investigated, which are presented in Figure 6. General observations are that pianists benefited most from auditory feedback at the low target force level, while for other factor combinations they performed only slightly better than non-musicians. An exception is the vibrotactile condition at medium target level, where non-musicians performed clearly worse than either of the musician groups. Other musicians performed evenly well at all factor combinations, and at medium target level even clearly better than the other two groups.

4. DISCUSSION

From the results described above for the employed setup, it can be generally concluded that audio-tactile feedback, and to a lesser degree auditory feedback alone, made it generally easier to reach a given target pressing-force, compared to the condition when no active feedback was present. Notably the results also show that the addition of the vibrotactile component to the auditory feedback generally improved the performance. The vibrotactile feedback alone looks instead less effective than the audio-tactile one.

The lower variance at the high target force further suggests that the task was easier with higher pressing force and more difficult at lower pressing forces. Thus one may accept the hypothesis that auditory, and especially audio-tactile feedback facilitate reaching force targets in condi-

Figure 6. Mean errors for non-musicians, pianists and other musicians, for low (top panel), medium (middle panel), and high (bottom panel) target forces.

tions where the task is difficult.

The performance of pianists – generally similar to that of non-musicians and under par compared to other musicians – may be explained considering that the task of pressing continuously on the touch box interface was clearly distant from that of hitting the keys on the piano. Moreover, in their instrumental practice, pianists are not in direct contact with the source of sound and vibration, which are instead mediated through the keys and hammer mechanics. This may result in less developed tactile sensitivity compared to e.g. players of stringed instruments, who perform by direct contact with the strings. In this regard, different studies [1, 20] showed that vibrations on stringed instruments are clearly perceivable by the player during performance, while vibrations on the piano are generally hardly felt at the fingers. It must be considered however that, due to difficulties in recruiting subjects, our sample size is small and it does not allow reliable statistical inference. As an example, a *Kruskal-Wallis test* on the “N-low target” combination was faintly non-significant ($\chi^2 = 4.86$, $p = 0.09$), giving no evidence for true differences in medians between the independent groups. Therefore it remains a future task to test more thoroughly performance differences among classes of musicians and non-musicians.

4.1 Issues

The experiment proved somewhat problematic at the high target force, where the results have a much lower variance than at the other two targets. The same is true for intra-subject variability: for all subjects the varying range of the 10 repetitions of each high-target conditions combination was typically much smaller than for the low or medium targets. One explanation lies in the nonlinear sensitivity curve of the touch box interface, shown in Figure 2), hence to equal small changes in the pressing-force correspond ADC values variations that are larger in the low range than in the high one. In this regard we plan to linearize the system, e.g. according to what suggested in [21]. Another explanation is that subjects found it easier to be accurate when

applying a hard rather than a soft pressing-force.

Fatigue was neither noticed in the recorded data, nor reported by the subjects. Practice effects during the course of the 10 repetitions of each combination of conditions were not observed, except during the first two repetitions for some subjects. However, future test designs should address the possible learning and kinesthetic memory effects, e.g. by varying the standard randomly within a narrow force range and presenting it before each trial.

Concerning the auditory feedback, according to the standardized equal loudness curves (ISO226:2003), the perceived loudness (phons) of a 200 Hz sine tone increases somewhat faster than the sound pressure level (dB) in the over 70 dB range than in the softer range, suggesting that a difference of 1 dB causes a greater difference in perceived loudness. However, in this occasion no loudness recordings could be performed, since at the time of writing we do not have instrumentation suitable for measurements on headphones.

Finally, it is known that sensitivity to vibrations depends on stimulus location, stimulus frequency and contact area [2]. In this regard, it is worth noticing that while most subjects performed the experiment placing their finger-pad on the touch panel, a few of them used their fingertip.

4.2 Other remarks

While visual feedback was not prevented explicitly, some subjects chose to perform the experiment with their eyes closed to better focus on the auditory and tactile sensations.

Related research involving memory in action-perception tasks is reported by Morris *et al.* [22], who found that haptic feedback enhanced force skill learning in sensorimotor tasks. Their study concerned visual and haptic force feedback and focused on the effect of three training modalities (visual only, haptic only, or both), while in the test phase the subjects relied only on force recall. In the present study, training was given to all subjects first without feedback and then with audio-tactile feedback, thus the effect of training on recall could not be measured. However it is expected that, in a normal musical scenario, the player learns the behavior of the instrument in presence of both auditory and haptic feedback.

An aspect requiring further measurements is that of the relative importance of kinesthetic and tactile feedback. In the present study, tactile feedback was in fact always present even in the neutral condition N through sensations of the fingertip, augmented by a vibrotactile signal in the V and AV feedback conditions. Thus it was not possible to completely separate the tactile and kinesthetic channels, as was done in a study by Srinivasan and Chen [23], who repeated force tracking experiments in normal conditions and with locally anesthetized finger tips. They found that while absence of tactile feedback resulted in somewhat higher force tracking errors, absence of augmented visual feedback increased the error with target force magnitude, indicating that without augmented visual feedback the force tracking task was more difficult with high target forces. This contradicts with our findings for high target forces, which indicate the smallest errors regardless of

feedback condition. Future experiments will be designed taking this aspect into account, while pressing forces will be measured in terms of Newtons instead of ADC values.

Also, we planned to perform vibration measurements on our interface for the different experimental conditions, and compare these data with known psychophysiological results [24].

Our choice of audio-tactile stimuli (sine wave) was motivated by the desire of keeping the setup as simple and controllable as possible. In future implementation we plan to consider the use of physically-based sound models that react in a dynamic way to the user's gestures. Nevertheless this could introduce interference at a cognitive and perceptual level that might be difficult to isolate in an experimental setting.

5. CONCLUSION

A pilot experiment has been described, which investigated the role of auditory and vibrotactile feedback in a finger-pressing task. At each trial, subjects had to aim at one of three memorized target pressing-forces, under different feedback conditions (no active feedback, audio only, vibrotactile only and audio-tactile). Our analysis show that the audio-tactile augmentation allowed subjects to reach a given target force with the best accuracy.

The present work is first in a series of planned experiments that will systematically measure performance for various musically relevant gesture primitives, in relation to auditory and haptic cues. In this way, we aim at providing useful guidelines for the implementation of future actuated digital musical instruments, that will enable improved performance control (e.g. precise timing, accurate intonation, articulation), expressivity and playability.

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